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QUANTIFICATION OF EXTERNAL COSTS FROM INCIDENTS IN RAIL TRANSPORT

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INTRODUCTION

Rail incidents¹ cause not only personal injury and material damage, but also operational complications all over the world. Irrespective of the level of infrastructure, they can never be completely prevented, but only eliminated through a series of preventive measures. The most common causes are collisions between a rail vehicle and another vehicle, an obstacle on the track, a collision with a car at a level crossing or a collision with a person. A certain category of incidents can be caused by lack of maintenance or low level of railway safety equipment. Incidents are also caused by human errors, which most often refers to signal passed at danger or damage to a traction line by the collector. However, in many countries the number of dangerous situations on the railways has not been successfully reduced and the value of damage has tended to stagnate, resulting in huge losses of life and property every year. Property losses are generally calculated for vehicles, infrastructure, and the environment, while the quantification of loss of life depends on the method chosen (more in chapter 1.1 Methodologies).

The objective of paper is to quantify the external costs of rail incidents. A secondary effect of transport are negative externalities, which include the externalities of traffic accidents. These externalities affect all actors in the traffic situation, even those not directly involved in the accident. The external costs methodologies from the reference list are used in the European Union, as well as the methodologies of the Transport Research Centre Czech Republic. In addition to these methodologies, calculations for the valuation of time losses are added. The use of existing methodologies is combined with the application of new methodologies. In this paper are calculated the incidents from the Czech Republic from 2017-2021 by individual years.

The negative external costs of accidents used in the calculations include many items that reflect the current trends in transport. Costs related to the value of human life include temporary or permanent disability and loss of productivity, with pain, health care costs, social costs, human losses and other additional costs. In the case of material losses of accidents, the social costs of accidents are assessed in terms of property damage, costs of rescue services, police, courts, administrative costs of legal services, activities of the authorities - Rail Safety Inspection Office

¹ The Law of Railways of the Czech Republic defines terms incident and accident as follows:

An incident occurs in connection with the operation of rail transport or the movement of a rail vehicle on or in the vicinity of the railway which endangers or disrupts:

- (a) the safety of rail transport
- (b) the safety of persons
- (c) the safe operation of structures or equipment; or
- (d) the environment.

An accident is caused by a collision or derailment of railway vehicles resulting in death, injury to at least five persons or extensive damage to a railway vehicle, the railway, or the environment as defined by the Criminal Code, or any other accident with similar consequences.

and other railway institutions, or administrative costs of insurance companies. Time values are set in categories according to passenger and freight transport. In passenger transport, the categories are further divided into working and non-working time, while in freight transport they are divided according to whether the goods transported are of high or low added value, or perishable goods. However, once the time values have been determined, it is essential to determine the amount of delay either for a single incident or for all incidents during the calendar year in the region and country considered [1]. To these damages should be added the costs of business interruption, IT support, staff overtime and their travel costs should also be added. All these costs must be taken into account.

1. EXTERNAL COSTS

The definition and calculation of negative externalities from traffic incidents has been the subject of several methodological approaches in Europe [4], [5], [6]. Based on the data collected, selected parameters for the calculation of externalities are determined, which are usually given for the price level of the selected year. If the calculation is for previous years, this value is increased by inflation to make the price in the current year relevant.

Each accident or incident quantifies material damage to vehicles, infrastructure and third parties, and sometimes environmental damage is quantified. Other damages consider the rest of consequences of these accidents.

1.1. METHODOLOGIES

Methodological approaches found in the literature [4], [6] often deal with total negative externalities as costs that are imposed on third parties that cannot be recovered from the originator or compensated by the market. One category of negative externalities is accidents. Traffic accidents are more problematic for rail than for road because of the limited traffic at the accident site, which results in significant time delay and losses.

This paper has been based on a few documents. Specific damage and cost calculations have been made in the Transport Research Centre's Methodology for Valuing Negative Externalities from Transport [2]. The advantage of this document is that it was prepared for the conditions of the Czech Republic, where this paper is also set. Therefore, all the parameters considered can be used and supplemented by additional parameters specific to railway sector. Other sources are methodologies and manuals that have been prepared uniformly for the whole European Union and are also generally applicable to all member states. However, the higher degree of generality of the parameters, the lower accuracy of the quantified results. All these relevant methodologies have been published by the European Commission [4], [5].

Transport Research Centre Czech Republic

The methodology of the Transport Research Centre Czech Republic deals with the quantification of all socio-economic losses caused by traffic accidents. Socio-economic losses include both material losses and losses from personal consequences. For the purposes of this paper, only the category of personal consequences will be investigated, as material losses are quantified in standard practice and are not classified as externalities.

Human casualties refer to people injured or killed in a traffic accident. They are classified as health care costs or social expenditure (pensions or sick leave during periods of incapacity to work) that would not have been occurred without the impact of the accident. An important component of these costs due to accidents is lost productivity, i.e., lost output, and friction costs. In the case of fatalities, funeral costs are included. Finally, human losses resulting from the accident are also considered. Human losses include loss or reduction in quality of life, pain, suffering, or total years of life lost compared to the life expectancy of the country. Costs are calculated for a calendar year, and people injured or killed are uniformly included according to their actual condition up to 30 days after the accident [2].

A contributing source is also the Departmental Guideline for the Evaluation of Economic Effectiveness of Transport Construction Projects made by State Transport Infrastructure Fund Czech Republic, which contains appropriate calculations for the analysis and evaluation of railway operations based on universal guidelines and local conditions. The document is based on the Guide to Cost-Benefit Analysis of Investment Projects for the Period 2014-2020. The data from the document, which were used for the actual calculations, were adjusted to the current price level, as the values from 2017 were originally considered [3].

Methodologies of the European Commission

Handbook on the external costs of transport

Chapter 3 contains a list of all the relevant costs of rail accidents in five categories: human costs, medical costs, administrative costs, loss of production and other (and material damages to vehicles, infrastructure, freight, and property damage resulting from accidents, but that is not a type of external cost for this paper). Human costs are the largest item, but the results depend too much on the method chosen (the variability of the results is too high). Total and average accident costs are calculated using a top-down approach, starting with a few accidents and then calculating according to their type a severity. The accident statistics are taken from EU Accidents Database. For each member state of the European Union, values for these costs are set individually according to the number of accidents and the price levels, which also vary considerably between countries [4].

Developing Harmonised European Approaches for Transport Costing and Project Assessment

In rail transport, the level of damage is influenced by factors such as traffic volume, weather, maintenance, and collisions with other trains in service and with road traffic at level crossings. The methodological procedures consider two approaches. The bottom-up approach consists of estimating the marginal cost of an accident based on traffic volume and risk elasticity. The top-down approach estimates the total and average costs per accident from national statistics. This approach includes human loss costs for administration, health care and lost production. The

bottom-up approach considers only part of the accidents and costs; therefore, the calculated costs are lower than in the second approach [5].

Additional external costs

In the actual calculation of external costs and losses due to rail incidents, not only the loss categories mentioned in the methodologies are included, but also other categories are added. Some of the methodologies mentioned only deal with road transport, so it is necessary to add categories that also apply to rail transport in order to get a relevant calculation.

When an incident occurs, delay is a significant problem. It depends on whether the incident occurs on a national main line or a regional line, whether the operation on the line is restricted or completely closed and whether there are possibilities to use other lines. In the case of time delay, it is not only the loss of passengers but also other losses that are incurred by the carriers themselves. The most significant of these are commercial losses and loss of profit - in the case of long delays, fares have to be refunded in whole or in part, additional costs are incurred to compensate passengers, and they may be deterred from making the next journey and they use alternative mode of transport. In the event of a complete stoppage of services on a route, replacement bus services are often set up, incurring additional costs for staff, fuel, vehicle depreciation and bus hire if the train operator does not have its own buses. If a train is delayed due to an accident, there are additional costs for the operator in terms of staff overtime, IT support and depot costs. Of course, if an incident occurs on a busy line, the situation will have a negative impact on other trains throughout the network, so a multiplier effect must be considered [6].

2. QUANTIFICATION OF EXTERNAL COSTS IN THE CZECH REPUBLIC

Information on railway incidents is investigated and collected by the Rail Safety Inspection Office in the Czech Republic. Incidents include situations where only minor damage occur, the focus was on those accidents where fatalities or injuries occurred. The most serious accidents with human casualties always involve lengthy investigations by inspectors, delays and other costs that have been specified. Situations from 2017-2021 were examined. Losses were calculated individually for each year and then averaged. The values of these damages are given in euros for the sake of clarity.

Every year the Rail Safety Inspection Office evaluates the accidents that have occurred on the railways. In addition to the assessed material damage, the number of victims and injuries is determined. For accidents and incidents, a distinction is made between serious accidents involving loss of life and minor incidents involving only material damage. Although minor incidents are recorded and cause delays, they are not included in the calculation of the social cost of accidents. The following table shows the statistics of the incidents during the period indicated:

	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
All incidents	1161	1171	1228	1148	1146
Only serious accidents (deaths/injured)	275	253	273	263	212
Deaths	237	212	241	239	198
Injured	206	209	237	276	225

Table 1: Overview of accidents and human losses on the Czech railways in 2017-2021

The Transport Research Centre's document on socio-economic losses is calculated for the values in the price level of 2020. The values for the relevant years are adjusted for inflation in the Czech Republic. The values calculated from 2020 have been increased by almost 3.8% for 2021. The conversion from Czech crowns to euros was based on the average exchange rate for the whole of 2022, which is 24.5 Czech crowns to 1 euro.

2.1. PRODUCTIVITY LOSSES

Output loss calculations are broken down into deaths and injuries, with injuries further broken down into serious (with permanent consequences) and minor (requiring only some time to recover). Output losses are calculated from GDP data at current prices, by calculating annual output per average working-age person. Accident data are used to determine the average age of

the victim of a road traffic accident victim in the Czech Republic is determined, so that it is possible to calculate the average number of years remaining until retirement that can no longer be worked. The loss of production when a person is killed averages more than 18 years, so this value is multiplied by the annual amount of production of a person of working age.

As already mentioned above, injuries are classified as major and minor; for the sake of simplicity and the limited scope of this paper, they are presented together in the tables. Severe injuries and absence from work last on average 130 days, including recovery time, and are therefore considered to be a complete loss of work output. For the remaining period up to the end of working life and retirement, a 10% reduction in work capacity is assumed. In the case of a minor injury, the work capacity is already at full level after recovery. The average period of incapacity to work after a road traffic accident in the Czech Republic is 25 days; the lost production during these days is also included in the total.

Based on these average figures from the database of real road accidents in the Czech Republic, a unit cost of 810 531 euro per person killed and 55 020 euro per person injured is assumed. These amounts were multiplied by the number of persons killed and injured in rail accidents.

	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Deaths	192,10	171,83	195,34	193,72	160,49
Injured	11,33	11,50	13,04	15,19	12,38
Total	203,43	183,33	208,38	208,91	172,87
<i>Average</i>	<i>195,38</i>				

Table 2: Productivity losses (€ million)

2.2. HEALTH COSTS

Hospital costs include the following category. The personal insurance data show costs that are calculated between deaths and injuries. The highest costs of medical treatment for convalescence are recorded for the most seriously injured, who spend the longest time in hospital, i.e., 8500 euro per average patient. Deaths are also included in this category as they are recorded up to 30 days after the accident. It is therefore common for a person to be taken to hospital in a serious condition immediately after an accident and then to die in hospital after several days or weeks following an unsuccessful rescue attempt. The average cost per fatality is 6540 euro. For minor injuries, the average cost is 1230 euro per person. Other costs related to the injury are included in other categories.

	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Deaths	1,40	1,25	1,42	1,40	1,16
Injured	0,95	0,96	1,10	1,27	1,04
Total	2,35	2,21	2,52	2,67	2,2

<i>Average</i>	2,39
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Table 3: Health costs (€ million)

2.3. HUMAN LOSSES

The average age of death in traffic accidents was used in the calculations of lost productivity. From this age until the end of the productive life period, there was a loss of productivity; in addition to work-related problems, other non-material losses caused by the premature end of life have to be added.

The value of years of life lost can be determined using the willingness-to-pay method (WTP), which considers how much the respondents are willing to pay to reduce the risk of fatal injury in an accident. The value of a statistical life was taken from the study *The Value of a Statistical Life in Road Safety Context* and converted to the current price levels [7]. From the value of a full statistical life of 1 367 347 euro, the value of a productive life of 810 531 euro mentioned above was deducted, which further explains the difference of 556 816 euro [2].

The loss of quality of life also refers to the injured. For severely injured people, the amount of 15 % of the number of years of life lost was used, according to the document. Other costs were not included because they are estimated rather than empirical data that can be read and calculated from real sources. Pain and other negative accompanying psychological phenomena were not included in the calculations.

	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Lost years of life	131,97	118,05	134,19	133,08	110,25
Reduced quality of life	11,20	11,36	12,89	15,01	12,23
Total	143,17	129,41	147,08	148,09	122,48
<i>Average</i>	<i>138,05</i>				

Table 4: Human losses (€ million)

2.4. SOCIAL EXPENDITURE

The system of benefits differs from country to country. In the Czech Republic, there are currently regulations in force which guarantee the sickness insurance benefits and pensions, of which all pensions (except for old-age pensions) are relevant, namely invalidity, widow's, and orphan's pensions, which may result from an untimely death on the railway.

Sickness benefits are based on the average duration of incapacity for work and the average earnings in the country. The employer pays the sickness benefit for the employee during the period of sickness, after which the cost is borne by the state budget. It is assumed that disability

pensions are paid for serious injuries. The average annual amount of disability pensions has been multiplied by the average duration of their payment. Both widow's and orphan's pensions are paid to the survivors of the deceased; the method of payment and calculation is similar to the previous case. The amount of these payments is not high, and they belong to the smallest costs categories.

	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Injured	0,28	0,28	0,32	0,38	0,31

Table 5: Social costs (€ million)

2.5. ADMINISTRATIVE COSTS

After every serious accident resulting in death or injury, administrative work has to be carried out, which incurs additional costs. Because of the heavy agenda of the authorities, other activities could not be carried out, so we also include these costs as an externality of rail accidents.

When a serious accident occurs on the railways, several emergency services have to be called to the scene. In addition to the Rail Safety Inspection Office, the police, the integrated rescue system, and the fire brigade must also attend the scene. For the police, an average of 10 km is considered for the journey to the accident site, the return journey, the cost of fuel and the depreciation of the vehicle. To this amount must be added the cost of the police officer's work in the event of death or injury, as it takes several hours of work to record the event, cooperate with the Rail Safety Inspection Office, or carry out the investigation itself. There is a correlation that the more serious the accident with serious consequences, the longer the investigation takes; average investigation times were determined and then multiplied by the hourly rate of an average police officer. For a fatal accident, a police cost of around 400 euro is considered, so the cost is not very high compared to others.

More costly is the activity of the fire brigade, which often has to provide rescue at the scene, ensure that all the entire rescue work is carried out and secure the scene so that the safety risk in traffic safety is minimised. The calculation is based on the average cost of an intervention in the event of a fatal or injury accident, the values are derived from road accidents, but a large proportion of these occur at level crossings in collisions with trains, so the results are closer to reality. The highest cost is for an accident with serious injuries, where an amount of around 3400 euro is considered.

In the case of involving the court, a distinction is made between the costs of the courts and the administrative authorities, depending on whether the accident was a crime or an offence. Accidents at level crossings are most often involve a general offence, with signal failures and partial driver misconduct being recorded as offences, but each accident is assessed individually

by inspectors and other authorities. In the case of more serious accidents, the action of the administrative and judicial authorities must therefore be considered. The activity of judges and assistants is considered, with costs quantified based on the average hourly wage and the average hourly workload per case. The loss of earnings of witnesses is based on the average wage in the country. In the case of administrative authorities, the amount is calculated based on the average earnings in the average length of experience (which determines the amount of salary earned in the public sector) of the offender. Witness costs are calculated in the same way as for the judiciary.

Finally, it is necessary to consider the costs of insurance companies, which include the costs of settling claims after an accident and administrative costs. Fatal accidents are the most expensive category, with an average accident costing around 6160 euro.

	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Police	0,15	0,14	0,16	0,17	0,14
Firefighter	0,99	0,96	1,09	1,18	0,97
Courts and administrative proceedings	2	1,87	2,12	2,24	1,84
Insurance	2	1,86	2,11	2,20	1,81
Total	5,14	4,83	5,48	5,79	4,76

Table 6: Administrative costs (€ million)

2.6. TIME LOSSES

Loss of time is also an important category of externalities, although in this case the damage values are not nominally large. If there is an accident on the line, traffic on the line is restricted or completely closed, depending on the severity of the accident. When investigating serious accidents involving fatalities and injuries, the Rail Safety Inspection Office requests information from the relevant carriers operating on the line in concerned on how long the operations on the line were restricted and how long the train was delayed. Depending on the operations on the line and their frequency, other trains are also indirectly affected by delays, which are also partly delayed by the network effect and the reduced punctuality on the railway at the time of the restriction. The annual delays caused by all the incidents on the line are shown in the table below. This is a relatively small number for a year, as most delays are generally due to waiting for connecting services, natural disasters, or delays abroad on international train services. The delay times shown in the table have increased significantly in recent years, even though the number of incidents on the railways has stagnated. This is due to the higher severity of accidents in recent years and to the general state of the rail infrastructure, which has been massively modernised, particularly in recent years, and the large number of construction works has led to a significant increase in delays across the network, which has had an impact in all areas.

In addition to the delay data from the carriers, it was necessary to find out the average number of passengers to calculate the lost passenger hours. In the official statistics of the national passenger transport carrier Czech Railways and other carriers, the values for the total annual number of passengers and the average percentage of train occupancy are known, but some values had to be calculated separately. Therefore, a sample of typical trains of the Czech Railways was prepared, considering an international long-distance train (with the commercial name Railjet), a domestic long-distance train (InterPanter) and regional trains, electric (CityElefant, RegioPanter) and diesel multiple units (RegioNova), as about two thirds of the railway lines in the Czech Republic are not electrified due to their large number and density, which is one of the highest in the world (122 km of lines per 1000 km²). According to the annual reports of the railway carriers, the occupancy rate of passenger trains has been around 25% on average for a year. As occupancy rates obviously vary over time, particularly in 2020 and 2021, which were marked by the covid-19 pandemic, which was accompanied by a series of restrictive measures on freedom of movement, which also led to low use of public transport, this figure has always been pro-rated based on the total number of passengers carried in a year. Based on a 25% occupancy rate of the monitored trains, the average occupancy rate is 74 persons per train.

A similar calculation was made for freight transport, as accidents on railway lines affect both passenger and freight transport. The data on delays in hours were left as they were, only the data on goods transported were provided. According to the data provided by freight carriers operating in the Czech Republic, the average net tonnage of freight is 450 tonnes. By multiplying the hours of delay by these values of net tonnes of freight per average train, the delay data in tonne-hours were obtained.

The aim of the calculations was to obtain data in man-hours and tonne-hours from which time values could be obtained. Time values are given in the documents Developing Harmonised European Approaches for Transport Costing and Project Assessment and the Departmental Guideline for the Evaluation of Economic Effectiveness of Transport Construction Projects, where a distinction is made between time values for passenger and freight transport in different contexts. For passenger transport, a distinction is made between values in working and non-working time values for short and long journeys; for freight transport, a distinction is made between the mode of transport and the goods transported. In the case of passenger transport, 10% of working time is considered, the rest being non-working time; in the case of freight transport, apart from standard rail transport, common goods are considered, which are valued at an average rate. Taking this into account, the amount per passenger hour of delay is about 14.5 euro for passenger transport and less than 2 euro per tonne-hour for freight transport. Summary figures for time losses in millions of euro are given in Table 7.

	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
All incidents	1161	1171	1228	1148	1146

Delay (hours)	587	492	754	901	924
Passengers/train (average)	72	76	40	50	50
Passenger-hours	42 264	37 392	30 160	45 050	46 200
Tonnes/train (average)	428	436	453	443	450
Tonne-hours	251 236	214 512	341 562	399 143	415 800
Loss (€ million)	0,84	0,74	0,84	1,38	1,43

Table 7: Time losses

2.7. OTHER LOSSES

In addition to the costs, other losses that are common to railway operations are calculated. In the event of a serious accident, operations on the line are stopped and all trains on the infrastructure are delayed. Data from the Rail Safety Inspection Office shows that in the event of fatality or injury, it takes an average of 3 hours to close the line for investigation and recovery before full or partial service can be restored.

The most significant item in this category is the loss of business and profits for the carriers most affected by this waiting time. When there is an incident on the railway, traffic on the line is restricted and this causes considerable damage to the carriers. The method of calculating these losses has been introduced based on state compensation to passenger carriers. In the period 2018-2022, a discount of 75% of the price has been applied to students up to 26 years of age and pensioners over 65 years of age. The discount was subsequently reimbursed to the carriers by the state through compensation funds and this amount was published regularly. When recalculated at 100%, it was possible to know the total amount of profit that all the carriers in the country made from passenger transport. In 2019, the carriers' profits amounted to 127 million euro, approximately 14500 euro per hour. As the most frequent closure or restriction of services, on average and in terms of numbers, is 3 hours, this amount was multiplied by three.

However, this amount (profit per hour multiplied by three) relates to the entire railway network in the Czech Republic, so it had to be further reduced to the appropriate length of the line affected by the closure. The length of all lines in operation is currently 9358 km and there are 36 lines of different lengths. The average length of an individual line, after rounding, represents approximately 3% of the country's rail network. The calculation procedure considers the situation where an accident occurs, and the traffic restriction affects this one line and no others. The number of economic losses is therefore reduced to an average line, i.e., 3% of the rail network. The three-hour restriction of an accident per line is therefore 1305 euro. In practice, the economic loss is not only a loss of passengers who may prefer another mode of transport for their next journey, but also an obligation to refund fares in the event of increased delays for both national and international journeys.

Longer delays and loss of time also impose increased costs on the staff of the carrier, as they must work longer than originally expected. Specifically, in terms of staff, this includes depot staff, IT support and staff on the train involved in the accident itself. In the case of the depot and IT support, one employee is assumed, whereas for the train staff, usually two members of the train crew are generally involved, as an engine driver and a guard are required for the normal operation of the train. The cost of one hour's work is assumed to be 40 euro, including tax, as these are professions that are valued above the average on the labour market because of their expertise. The working time of one depot worker, one IT support worker and two train crew member is therefore increased by 3 hours, resulting in additional costs for the carrier.

In total, this amounts to 1785 euro per incident. This considers the number of incidents that occur on the rail network each year. This corresponds to an increased cost of around 2 million euro per year, as can be seen in Table 8 below.

	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Injured	2,07	2,09	2,19	2,05	2,05
<i>Average</i>	<i>2,09</i>				

Table 8: Social costs (€ million)

2.8. RESULTS

The costs of externalities from rail accidents were assessed in several categories, excluding material damage. Calculations for some categories were based on existing methodologies, which were individually adapted for use in rail transport. Other categories included all direct and indirect costs of rail incidents.

All losses over the five years studied are shown in Table 9, with productivity and human losses according for the largest share of costs. The costs are calculated from the total number of incidents, fatalities and injuries, the results are similar each year. The average for this period is around 350 million euro per year.

	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Productivity losses	203,43	183,33	208,38	208,91	172,87
Health costs	2,35	2,21	2,52	2,67	2,2
Human losses	143,17	129,41	147,08	148,09	122,48
Social costs	0,28	0,28	0,32	0,38	0,31
Administrative costs	5,14	4,83	5,48	5,79	4,76
Time losses	0,48	0,43	0,35	0,65	0,67
Other losses	2,07	2,09	2,19	2,05	2,05
Total	356,92	322,58	366,32	368,54	305,34

<i>Average</i>	<i>343,94</i>
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Table 9: All types of costs (€ million)

3. CONCLUSIONS

To express the calculated values in relative terms, the ratio to the expenditure on transport infrastructure within the State Transport Infrastructure Fund Czech Republic was chosen. This fund redistributes money for transport infrastructure by collecting national and European funds, which are then used for infrastructure construction and maintenance. Rail expenditure is the largest component of transport infrastructure expenditure, typically accounting for 40-55% of total costs.

Table 10: Modal share of expenditure on transport infrastructure in years 2017-2021 (%)

During the period under review, spending on rail infrastructure increased massively, almost doubling, driven by the expansionary fiscal policy of the then Czech government and the increased share of investment during the COVID-19 pandemic to support the domestic economy. The share of calculated external costs therefore falls from 25% to 12%. As these are large sums of money, infrastructure costs account for a significant part of these costs.

	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Expenses on rail infrastructure	1377,99	1736,4	1790,54	2219,1	2541,76
Total costs	356,92	322,58	366,32	368,54	305,34
Costs to expenses ratio (%)	25,9	18,6	20,5	16,6	12

Table 11: Quantification of ratio (€ million)

Quantifying the damage and external costs of incidents is not just a statistical indicator but can also have practical applications. In many cases, this may involve the protection of high-risk level crossings or railway lines with higher accident rates, where the investment costs may be

high, but the benefits may outweigh them. These calculations will make it possible to carry out a cost-benefit analysis (CBA) of the increased safety investment. In the case of many incidents at the same site, the total quantified damage already incurred can be compared with the cost of the safety investment, which can significantly reduce the likelihood of another incident of the same or similar type. From a safety perspective, these are costly investments, and by calculating the potential savings from future damage, it is possible to determine the likely rate of return on investment, or whether a costly investment is an economically viable solution to the situation.

Possibilities for further research include refining the data by individual accident. For example, in the case of human and productivity losses, the average age of the victim is considered based on the available data. Determining the exact age of each victim would help to provide more accurate values for production losses, as it would be clear how many years of the victim's working life were left. In general, further research could focus on more detailed individual accident data and less on averages, which would make the results of losses and externalities more precise.

In addition to quantified losses, the use of the results, for example in the CBA mentioned above, should also be considered. In the context of the research activity, losses should be seen as a social cost that can be reduced or eliminated by introducing measures and investments in safety. This could apply not only to the level crossings mentioned, but also to investments in other safety equipment such as European Train Control System (ETCS), expansion of operator's control rooms, reduction of train drivers' working hours, etc. There are several safety measures that could further improve rail safety.

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